
DIGITAL PAYMENTS REGULATORY LANDSCAPE IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Digital payment platforms such as UPI, mobile wallets, and online banking have rapidly transformed financial transactions and payments in India towards a cashless economy. While digitization has enabled convenience, accessibility and growth, it has also brought complex legal implications surrounding privacy, security, consumer rights and regulatory gaps. This study comprehensively analyses the legal landscape governing digital payments in India across dimensions of regulatory frameworks, data privacy, consumer protection, anti-money laundering and taxation. It examines the existing laws and regulations including the “Payment and Settlement Systems Act 2007,” directions by regulatory bodies like RBI, as well as emerging issues due to fintech innovations. The research identifies limitations, challenges and threats arising from the increasing digitization of payments. It aims to provide recommendations focused on modernizing outdated regulations, enhancing consumer safeguards, balancing innovation with risk management and coordinating between regulatory authorities. The study intends to cover the multifaceted legal aspects of digital payments in India and contribute insights into strengthening this rapidly growing system by addressing risks and bridging regulatory gaps. The key objectives are to analyze the current legal and policy infrastructure, identify issues and gaps, and provide suggestions to promote safe, inclusive and innovative digital payment ecosystems aligned with global best practices.

KEYWORDS: Digital Payments, Legal Implications, Regulatory Frameworks, Consumer Protection & Data Privacy

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I. INTRODUCTION

The Indian economy has advanced rapidly, particularly with the rise of e-commerce, electronic payments, and digital transactions. Electronic payments have been increasing due to demonetisation, and the present administration is actively promoting this payment method. The younger, technologically adept population is increasingly utilising electronic payment methods, with over 140 crore rupees being traded daily across various electronic payment platforms.¹ Various governments have different goals, with a focus on providing internet connectivity to remote regions to enable seamless payment transactions for the residents. With the widespread use of electronic payment systems, several instances of fraud have occurred. To address this issue, different laws have been created and enforced in India and globally.²

In India, the *“Payment and Settlement Systems Act, 2007” (PSS /Act)* is the principal legislation governing payments. The primary purpose of the PSS Act is to oversee systemically significant payment systems, with the RBI serving as the regulator. The PSS Act primarily focuses on systemic regulation and grants regulatory authority to the RBI without establishing equivalent requirements for payment system operators on key concerns. In order to supervise payment systems and remedy these shortcomings, the RBI has used its power to issue directions under the PSS Act. In accordance with the PSS Act, the RBI has published around 280 notifications and circulars since its implementation. Due to a lack of explicit guidance in the primary statute, India's regulatory framework for payment systems has evolved entirely via secondary legislation.³

The comprehensive set of rules governing e-wallets and payment aggregators, including authorization requirements under the PSS Act, operational guidelines, risk management obligations, consumer protection measures, and interoperability standards, are established through subordinate legislation. The payment industry has experienced significant changes due to the implementation of the PSS Act, leading to the introduction of new participants and services in retail payments. The PSS Act has remained unchanged since it was enacted over ten

¹ Ranjith, P. V., Swati Kulkarni, and Aparna J. Varma. "A literature study of consumer perception towards digital payment mode in India." *Psychology and Education* 58, no. 1 (2021): 3304-3319.

² Singh, Shamsher, and Ravish Rana. "Study of consumer perception of digital payment mode." *Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce* 22, no. 3 (2017): 1-14.

³ Ramlall, Indranarain. "Payment and Settlement Systems." In *Economic Areas Under Financial Stability*, vol. 4, pp. 27-45. Emerald Publishing Limited, (2018).

years ago. There is a lack of required laws to provide a favorable environment for retail payments, such as provisions to encourage competition, innovation, and consumer protection.⁴

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The objective of this research is to comprehensively analyze the legal and regulatory landscape surrounding digital payment systems in India. Specifically, the research aims to:

1. Examine the existing laws, regulations, and policy frameworks governing digital payments in India.
2. Identify regulatory gaps, challenges, and opportunities to strengthen the digital payments ecosystem.
3. Explore emerging legal issues and implications related to digital payments, including privacy, security, consumer protection, anti-money laundering, and taxation.
4. Provide recommendations for modernizing regulations and addressing legal issues to promote innovation and growth of digital payments.

III. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What are the existing laws, regulations, and regulatory bodies governing digital payments in India? What are their limitations?
2. What are the major legal issues and challenges associated with digital payments in areas such as privacy, security, consumer protection, AML, and taxation?
3. How can policies and regulations for digital payments be modernized to address emerging threats while enabling innovation?
4. How can consumer interests, especially those related to privacy and security, be safeguarded in the context of increasing digital payments?

⁴ Badruddin, Aisha. "Financial Market Infrastructures: A Study on Payment and Settlement System in Indian Banking Sector." *International Journal of Engineering Technology, Management and Applied Sciences* 3, no. 2 (2015): 180-191.

IV. SCOPE OF THE RESEARCH

The scope of the research encompasses analysing laws, regulations, and policy frameworks at both central and state government levels that impact digital payment services in India. It examines regulatory approaches of major statutory bodies such as RBI, SEBI, TRAI, and Ministry of Finance that govern aspects of digital payments including mobile banking, mobile wallets, UPI, cards, net banking, and newer fintech innovations. The study delves into emerging risks, gaps, and legal issues associated with digital payments and provides recommendations focused on modernizing regulations, addressing legal implications, enhancing consumer protection, and enabling competition and innovation while mitigating risks.

V. MODERNISING THE LAW FOR PAYMENT SERVICES IN INDIA

The payment industry is undergoing a fast transformation due to technological advancements. There is a fresh push to establish rules and laws that facilitate the expansion of digital payment systems, as the payments industry innovates to satisfy customer demand for quicker, more secure, and more inventive payment methods.

The payments industry is undergoing fast change, and several nations have updated their payments laws to reflect this trend. These new laws use activity-based and risk-based methods. The goals of retail payment system modernization include increasing security, efficiency, innovation, and competition. The Singapore, United Kingdom, Australia, Hong Kong, Indonesia, Canada, and Brazil are seven of the selected countries that have a large amount of digital payments and a low volume of cash transactions. The Report examines the principal laws that regulate payments in these jurisdictions.⁵

Many countries like the Singapore, UK, and Hong Kong differentiate between payment systems and payment services. Payment systems facilitate money transfers, while payment

⁵ “Modernising the Law for Payment Services in India” (Oxford Law Blogs, November 3, 2021) <<https://blogs.law.ox.ac.uk/business-law-blog/blog/2021/11/modernising-law-payment-services-india#:~:text=In%20India%2C%20the%20PSS%20Act,the%20regulator%20of%20payment%20systems>> accessed February 27, 2024.

services directly interact with customers. This distinction helps categorize the various players in the payments industry and develop appropriate regulations for each.⁶

Most of these countries have set up a system to authorize payment services and designate systemically important payment systems that could pose broader financial risks. These risky payment systems face more stringent oversight to guard against destabilizing the wider financial system.

Three main goals steer the rules and supervision around consumer payments: *1)* Ensuring payment systems are stable and well-managed *2)* Promoting efficiency in how payment systems function *3)* Safeguarding consumer interests when using payment services.⁷

The PSS Act is the main statute in India that regulates payments. The primary objective of the PSS Act was to provide a framework for the regulation of systemically significant payment systems. The RBI, which is India's central bank, was entrusted with this responsibility. Because of its limited initial scope, the PSS Act grants the RBI regulatory authority and regulates the system as a whole, but it does not impose any duties on payment system operators with respect to fundamental concerns. With its authority to give directives under the PSS Act, the RBI has addressed these inadequacies by regulating payment systems.⁸

The RBI has used the PSS Act to publish around 280 circulars and notifications since the law's passage. This resulted in a scenario where the main law did not provide any particular advice and the whole regulatory framework for payment systems in India grew via secondary legislation. To provide just one example, subordinate legislation is the source of the entire regulatory framework for e-wallets and payment aggregators, including the PSS Act's authorization requirements, substantive provisions for the operation of these payment services, and obligations regarding risk management, consumer protection, interoperability, and so on.⁹

Since the implementation of the PSS Act, the payments industry has seen significant transformations due to the rise of new participants and services in retail payments. The PSS

⁶ "Modernising the Law for Payment Services in India" (Oxford Law Blogs, November 3, 2021) <<https://blogs.law.ox.ac.uk/business-law-blog/blog/2021/11/modernising-law-payment-services-india#:~:text=In%20India%2C%20the%20PSS%20Act,the%20regulator%20of%20payment%20systems>> accessed February 27, 2024.

⁷ Maw, Khin Thida. "Development of Payment and Settlement System." *Economic Reforms in Myanmar: Pathways and Prospects* (2013).

⁸ Roy, Deepankar, and Amarendra Sahoo. "Payment systems in India: Opportunities and challenges." *Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce* 21, no. 2 (2016): 1.

⁹ "Modernising the Law for Payment Services in India" (Oxford Law Blogs, November 3, 2021) <<https://blogs.law.ox.ac.uk/business-law-blog/blog/2021/11/modernising-law-payment-services-india>> accessed February 27, 2024.

Act has remained unchanged since it was enacted over ten years ago. There is a lack of required laws to provide a favourable environment for retail payments, such as measures that encourage competition, and innovation, and safeguard customers.

The Payment Services Act has to be revised to incorporate newly introduced payment services and take into account the shifting landscape of the payments business. To monitor financial transactions, India ought to enact a separate piece of law that has the important qualities listed below. To do this, the PSS Act would need to be modified so that it does not include payment services that are under the purview of clearing and settlement systems.

We need to include a definition of 'payment services' that encompasses the latest consumer-oriented payment services that are developing. Identifying these services will provide clarity to new enterprises and aid in creating an efficient regulatory environment by preventing redundancies and duplications.

Regulation should be commensurate to the risks associated with a payment service, using a risk-based approach. This enables new enterprises to experiment freely while ensuring that businesses engaged in high-risk activities are closely regulated. The legislation should establish a two-tiered regulatory system that includes authorization criteria for “payment service providers” (PSPs) and a framework for designating systemically significant payment systems.¹⁰

The proposed payment services law aims to provide a comprehensive framework governing various aspects of payment systems and protecting consumer interests. In terms of risk management, the law should lay out clear principles and requirements for PSPs to have robust operational risk management policies and procedures. This includes having systems to prevent, detect, and respond to operational disruptions from fraud, cyber-attacks, system failures etc. that could impact payment services.

Regarding consumer protection, the law must enforce obligations requiring PSPs to communicate clearly with consumers on terms, fees, transaction records, dispute resolution mechanisms and data policies. Consumers need assurances of confidentiality of personal data,

¹⁰ Rajisha, T. "Payment Banking in India-Its Scope and Importance in Present Scenario." ZENITH International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research 8, no. 3 (2018): 108-121.

limiting liability for unauthorized transactions, having accessible grievance redressal channels and compensation for losses due to PSP's fault.¹¹

To promote fair access and innovation, the law should enable interoperability between different payment systems, channels and instruments through common technology standards. It should restrict anti-competitive practices and ensure smaller PSPs can access the core payment infrastructure in a transparent, equitable manner.

In addition, PSPs would need to assess risks before outsourcing services to third-party partners that support critical payment functions. PSPs must inform regulators of key service provider appointments or terminations, assuming accountability for such providers' actions. This oversight would incentivize careful partner selection and monitoring by PSPs.

It is the goal of the legislation governing payment services to strike a balance between sensible risk management, consumer rights, and equitable market access. This will create an environment that is conducive to the safe and efficient execution of cashless transactions on a large scale. Achieving this objective would be facilitated by the specific regulatory and compliance duties that have been outlined. Even though the adoption of digital payments is determined by a number of demand and supply side variables, a legislative environment that is favourable to the ongoing usage of such payments by all customer groups is a crucial enabler for the promotion of digital payments.¹²

VI. SECURITY AND PRIVACY OF DIGITAL PAYMENTS IN INDIA

In India, data protection viz. private parties are currently governed by *“the Information Technology Act, 2000 (as amended) (IT Act)* and more specifically, the rules issued under *Section 43A of the IT Act: Information Technology (Reasonable Security Practices and Procedures and Sensitive Personal Data or Information) Rules, 2011 (Data Protection Rules).*”¹³

¹¹ RAMARATNAM, MS, and R. JAYARAMAN. "ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN ENHANCING THE EFFECTIVE FUNCTIONING OF INDIAN FINANCIAL SYSTEM: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY." (2011)

¹² Narendra Kumar, N. V., Abhishek Thakur, G. Raghuraj, and S. Lalit Mohan. "The payment systems revolution: India's story." *Journal of Payments Strategy & Systems* 14, no. 4 (2020): 326-338.

¹³ Hassan, Md Arif, Zarina Shukur, Mohammad Kamrul Hasan, and Ahmed Salih Al-Khaleefa. "A review on electronic payments security." *Symmetry* 12, no. 8 (2020): 1344.

India's IT Act defines two main classes of personal information that are relevant from a data privacy protection standpoint.

The first category is Personal Information (PI) - any data that relates to an identified or identifiable natural person. For example, name, address, date of birth, ID numbers, location data, online identifiers etc. Even if the data does not directly identify a person, it would be considered PI if it can reasonably be linked to an individual by combining it with other accessible information.

The second more sensitive category is "Sensitive Personal Data or Information" (SPDI). This includes financial information such as bank account and payment instrument details that can be misused for fraud or identity theft. Health data like physical, mental and physiological conditions, and medical history also need tight control as it risks insurance/employment discrimination. Sexual orientation data likewise merits heightened confidentiality. Other SPDI would be passwords and biometric data like fingerprints or eye scans used for authentication by UIDAI's Aadhaar ecosystem in India.¹⁴

Essentially, while all personal data merits security, SPDI data directly risks enabling crime or more severe harm if compromised. Thus, the IT Act distinguishes SPDI as warranting additional consent, encryption and access control mechanisms to prevent significant adverse impacts on data principals. The rapid growth of digital payments and healthcare along with national biometric IDs have made such SPDI regulations essential in India though standards still need further development.

District Registrar and Collector, Hyderabad vs. Canara Bank (2005)¹⁵ The court ruled that a bank is liable to its customers for unauthorized electronic transactions if security lapses are attributed to the bank. This established precedent for banks being liable for security issues in online transactions. In ***Vijay Aggarwal Vs. ICICI Bank Limited (2016)***¹⁶ The consumer forum held a bank liable for the loss of funds due to identity theft and a SIM swap scam, even when the customer's phone was involved in the fraudulent transactions. The bank was fined for negligence in security practices.

Right to Privacy

¹⁴ Li, Zengpeng, Vishal Sharma, and Saraju P. Mohanty. "Preserving data privacy via federated learning: Challenges and solutions." *IEEE Consumer Electronics Magazine* 9, no. 3 (2020): 8-16.

¹⁵ With C.A. 7079 of 2004 (Arising out of SLP (C) No. 11607/2001)

¹⁶ Complaint No. CC/147/2010

The case of *Justice K. Puttaswamy (A.D.) vs the Indian Union*¹⁷ is a vibrant victory for the right to privacy. In this case, “the constitutional validity of the Indian biometric identity scheme's Aadhar card was questioned. This was the turning point in Indian history as the right to privacy has been upheld by the country’s highest court. The nine judges unanimously agreed that the right to privacy is protected as an integral part of the right to life and personal freedom under Article 21 and as part of the freedoms guaranteed by Part III of the Constitution.”

The rules that safeguard personal information in India have certain holes in them. If an organisation handles sensitive personal data, it is required by Section 43 A of the Information Technology Act to implement reasonable security practices. Failing to do so will result in the organisation being held liable for the consequences, and the body will be required to pay for those consequences. In addition, many e-government initiatives depend on vast volumes of data, which makes the issue of data security much more difficult to solve and creates additional worries over data protection.

The IT Act, 2000 is the primary legislation dealing with cybercrimes including online fraud in India. Several key sections address specific types of frauds and unauthorized activities conducted using computers, networks or electronic means.

- **Section 43** prescribes penalties if someone accesses or uses another person's computer system or network without permission, resulting in damages. This covers unauthorized access which can enable online fraud.
- **Section 65** deals with the falsification, alteration or destruction of computer source documents like code or data to commit fraud - for instance manipulating an organization's source code or records stored digitally in databases.
- **Section 66** addresses a wide spectrum of computer-related offenses including phishing, identity theft, hacking, data theft and using computers/networks to defraud people through misrepresentation or deception.
- **Section 66C** exclusively focuses on identity theft where someone fraudulently uses other's personal information or electronic signature to wrongfully gain or cause loss. This is common in online financial frauds.
- **Section 66D** covers online cheating by impersonation where an individual pretends to be someone else using electronic channels to deceitfully take money or property from victims.

¹⁷ Writ Petition (Supreme Court) (Civil) No.494 of 2012

- While **Section 66E** deals with violation of privacy by capturing or transmitting private images without consent, it has relevance in sextortion cases involving blackmail and extortion.
- **Section 72** addresses breach of confidentiality if services providers violate privacy of information accessed contractually. This data could then be misused to defraud people through unauthorized access.¹⁸

It is important to note that in April 2018, the RBI issued the Storage of Payment System Data Directive, 2018 ("Data Storage Circular"), which required all system providers to store all data pertaining to payment systems in one repository in India. The data included in this message or payment instruction should include all the necessary elements of the transaction, including all information acquired, carried, and processed. Information related to a transaction's overseas leg is not required to be stored in this way per this Data Storage Circular. This requirement has a compliance deadline of October 15, 2018.

The "Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023" (DPDP Act), which was released by the Government of India on August 11, 2023, is currently a component of India's personal data protection and regulatory framework. The DPDP Act takes a comprehensive approach to the duties of financial companies, and PSP is not left out of this. The DPDP Act has far-reaching consequences for the payments industry, which we have examined in this paper along with potential solutions.¹⁹

When it comes to the gathering, processing, storing, and transmitting of digital personal data, the DPDP Act brings several compliances. Still, the government may have to do more to get the DPDP Act into effect, including announcing the rules and regulations needed to put it into effect and enforce it. Data that is neither personally identifiable nor stored in a digital format are exempt from regulation under the DPDP Act. Because of this, there are presently no rules governing the gathering and processing of non-personal data in India.²⁰

The DPDP Act is formulated with several guiding principles to ensure that personal data is handled responsibly by organizations. These principles include ensuring lawful, fair, and

¹⁸ Nishith Desai Associates, Privacy and Data Protection in India, (June 2023) <https://nishithdesai.com/fileadmin/user_upload/pdfs/Research_Papers/Privacy-and-Data-Protection-in-India.pdf> accessed February 27, 2024.

¹⁹ Khang, Alex, Vrushank Shah, and Sita Rani, eds. "Handbook of Research on AI-Based Technologies and Applications in the Era of the Metaverse." IGI Global, (2023).

²⁰ "Law in India - DLA Piper Global Data Protection Laws of the World" <<https://www.dlapiperdataprotection.com/index.html?t=law&c=IN>> accessed February 27, 2024.

transparent usage of personal data, limiting data usage to its intended purpose, collecting only necessary information, maintaining data accuracy, storing data for only as long as necessary, implementing safeguards against unauthorized access or processing, and holding accountable the entity responsible for determining how personal data is processed, known as the Data Fiduciary.

The scope of the DPDP Act extends to the processing of digital personal data within India, whether collected digitally or converted into digital form later. It applies to both Indian entities processing personal data and foreign entities offering goods or services to individuals within India, thereby ensuring extraterritorial applicability.

However, certain exemptions exist, such as personal data used for personal or domestic purposes and data deliberately made public by law or by the individual to whom it relates.

For PSPs, who act as Data Processors under the DPDP Act, there are specific implications and requirements:²¹

1. **Consent Mechanisms:** Consent for data processing must be freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous, with clear affirmative action. Traditional click-wrap options may no longer suffice, necessitating changes in consent request mechanisms.
2. **Handling Child Transaction Data:** Transactions involving children require special care and additional security measures. PSPs need to develop mechanisms to identify such transactions and individuals.
3. **Data Breach Reporting:** Any instance of a data breach must be promptly reported to the Data Protection Board, the affected customers, and the bank. PSPs may appoint a reporting officer for this purpose.
4. **Data Access, Correction, and Erasure:** PSPs must facilitate Data Principals' requests for accessing, correcting, and erasing their data, potentially requiring the development of a dedicated portal for such requests.

²¹ Tiwari A, "FIG Paper (No. 27 – Data Law Series 1): Implications of Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023, on Payment Service Providers | India Corporate Law" (India Corporate Law, December 1, 2023) <<https://corporate.cyrilamarchandblogs.com/2023/11/fig-paper-no-27-series-1-implications-of-digital-personal-data-protection-act-2023-on-payment-service-providers/#:~:text=Audit%20Requirements%3A%20Under%20the%20DPDP,by%20CERT%2DIn%20empanell ed%20auditors>> accessed February 27, 2024.

Besides the DPDP Act, PSPs must also adhere to sectoral regulations, which entail:²²

1. **Cross-Border Data Transfer:** While the DPDP Act doesn't restrict cross-border data transfer except to specified countries, the RBI mandates that all data of system providers be stored only in India, prohibiting cross-border data transfer.
2. **Audit Requirements:** While periodic audits are required under the DPDP Act for "Significant Data Fiduciaries" (SDFs), Payment Aggregators need to submit system audit reports, including cybersecurity audits. Clarification is needed on whether these reports can serve the purpose of both data and cybersecurity audits.
3. **Security Measures:** PSPs must implement technical and organizational measures to prevent data breaches, in addition to complying with RBI's Information Security Policy and various security mechanisms.
4. **Grievance Redressal:** PSPs must provide accessible grievance redressal mechanisms and respond within prescribed time limits. However, clarity is needed regarding the specific grievance redressal process for PSPs' Data Principals.

Overall, PSPs need to ensure compliance with both the DPDP Act and sectoral regulations to safeguard personal data and maintain the integrity and security of their operations.

VII. PROTECTION OF CONSUMERS' RIGHTS IN ELECTRONIC TRANSACTION

Who is a consumer? A consumer is someone who purchases things or services in exchange for money, whether fully or partially, or via a delayed payment system, and also includes those who utilise the items or benefit from the services. According to the Consumer Protection Act 2019, the terms "buys any goods" and "hires or avails any services" include transactions conducted offline or online using electronic means, teleshopping, direct selling, or multi-level marketing.²³

²² Deshmukh SM, Vajpayee S and Telecom E, "India's Digital Transformation: A Deep Dive into Data Protection Act" (ETTelecom.com, August 17, 2023) <<https://telecom.economictimes.indiatimes.com/blog/indias-digital-transformation-a-deep-dive-into-data-protection-act/102786525>> accessed February 27, 2024.

²³ Nomani, M. Z. M., Faizanur Rahman, and Alaa KK Alhalboosi. "Consumer Protection Act, 2019 and its implications for the medical profession and health care services in India." Journal of Indian academy of forensic medicine 41, no. 4 (2019): 282-285.

The RBI has issued consumer protection standards for payment service providers to ensure swift resolution of complaints and dispute resolution. Consumers have the right to pursue legal action in cases of fraudulent transactions or disputes, and providers must collaborate with law enforcement authorities to prevent fraud. The rapid expansion of online payments in India, driven by the e-commerce sector and government programs like Digital India, has heightened financial transactions' ease and effectiveness, but also raised concerns about consumer safety due to sensitive financial information and increasing cyber threats.²⁴

Data privacy and security are among the main issues. Online payment systems gather and retain a large quantity of personal data, which exposes them to data breaches and unauthorised entry. The Information Technology Act of 2000 and its revisions try to tackle data privacy issues, although questions persist about its effectiveness in the ever-changing online payment environment. Consumers often find it challenging to comprehend intricate terms and conditions, thereby jeopardising their privacy due to ambiguous permission methods.

Another issue is fraudulent transactions and unauthorised charges. Phishing schemes, virus incursions, and unauthorised use of stolen credentials may result in substantial financial losses for customers. The “Consumer Protection Act, 2019, and the Consumer Protection (E-commerce) Rules, 2020,” provide guidelines for resolving issues, however, consumers typically have the responsibility of proving fault, leading to a complex and prolonged procedure.

Enhancing consumer protection requires a multifaceted strategy. Firstly, rigorous data security standards and severe enforcement procedures are important. Enforcing more stringent data protection regulations, such as the European Union's “General Data Protection Regulation” (GDPR), might provide a more thorough structure for data management. Secondly, it is crucial to promote financial literacy and raise knowledge about safe online payment methods. Empowering customers with education on hazards, phishing methods, and safe password practices enables them to make educated decisions.²⁵

Thirdly, it is crucial to promote a collaborative strategy that includes stakeholders such as payment service providers, banks, and regulatory agencies. Utilising multi-factor authentication, robust encryption techniques, and real-time transaction monitoring may greatly

²⁴ Poorna, S. Jothi. "a Critical Analysis of Consumer Protection Act 2019." *Supremo Amicus* 15 (2020): 283.

²⁵ Wronka, Christoph. "“Cyber-laundering”: the change of money laundering in the digital age." *Journal of Money Laundering Control* 25, no. 2 (2022): 330-344.

decrease the likelihood of fraud. Improving grievance redressal systems and promptly resolving concerns would boost customer trust.

It is crucial to encourage responsible innovation in the financial industry. Utilising blockchain technology, artificial intelligence for fraud detection, and open-source solutions may create a more secure and inclusive online payment system.

VIII. ONLINE MONEY LAUNDERING AND FRAUD

There is a possibility that digital payment systems might be susceptible to fraud and money laundering. To address these concerns, the RBI has implemented KYC standards as well as AML rules. As a result of these efforts, financial institutions are required to verify the identities of their clients and keep an eye out for any suspicious activity that may occur during transactions. If these requirements are not adhered to, there may be serious legal repercussions, including the possibility of criminal prosecution. Providers of digital payment services are required to undertake stringent anti-money laundering and know their customer processes.²⁶

The "*Prevention of Money Laundering Act, 2002*" (PMLA) along with the "*Prevention of Money Laundering (Maintenance of Records) Rules, 2005*" (Rules) are that India passed to combat the practice of money laundering. The "Reserve Bank of India / Securities and Exchange Board of India/Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India" is one of the specialist bodies in India that deals with money laundering concerns; it also publishes advice on anti-money laundering standards based on PMLA and Rules.

KYC regulations are required to be implemented by the RBI to verify the identification of clients. It is possible to face legal consequences if proper know your customer checks are not performed. In accordance with anti-money laundering legislation, financial institutions, including those that provide digital payment services, are obligated to keep an eye out for suspicious activity and report it to the appropriate authorities. There can be significant legal consequences, including criminal charges if compliance is not demonstrated. Payment service providers must make substantial investments in fraud protection technologies to safeguard not

²⁶ Goecks, "Anti-money laundering and financial fraud detection: A systematic literature review." *Intelligent Systems in Accounting, Finance and Management* 29, no. 2 (2022): 71-85.

only themselves but also their clients against fraudulent occurrences. It is possible to incur legal responsibility if you fail to do so.²⁷

Reserve Bank of India vs. Zahid Hasan (2018) involved a challenge to the RBI's directive mandating mandatory KYC for Prepaid Payment Instruments (PPIs) like mobile wallets. The Supreme Court upheld the RBI's directive, highlighting the importance of KYC norms in preventing money laundering and other financial crimes. While not directly addressing online e-KYC, it emphasizes the significance of KYC procedures in the digital payments realm.

In India, gaining access to banking services and conducting transactions online has never been simpler than it is right now. The emergence of a flourishing financial ecosystem may be attributed to the convergence of forward-thinking legislation with ground-breaking technologies.²⁸

The process of digitization has consequently been a sword with two edges. The heading of the section: A concise summary of India's journey into the digital realm One of the most important factors that is driving digitalization in India is the "Digital Public Infrastructure" (DPI) of India. With the addition of DigiLocker in 2015, UPI in 2016, GSTN in 2017, and the most recent Account Aggregator feature in 2021, India Stack has shown constant growth since the introduction of Aadhaar in 2009. The use of this technology has made it possible for suppliers of financial services to develop new financial instruments, credit paths, and products for clients, all of which are designed to improve the entire experience and boost convenience. The outcomes of these advances include the convenience with which debit and credit cards may be accessed, the integration of UPI across various platforms, the growth of online banking facilities, and the simplicity with which low-value debit and credit cards can be opened.²⁹

IX. REGULATIONS AND GUIDELINES FORMULATED BY SEBI, IRDAI & RBI

A. REGULATIONS/ GUIDELINES BY THE RBI

²⁷ Bailey, Rishab, Trishee Goyal, Renuka Sane, and Ridhi Varma. "Analysing India's KYC Framework: Can We Do Things Better?." *Available at SSRN 3776008* (2021).

²⁸ Cristian Alonso, Tanuj Bhojwani, Emine Hanedar, Dinar Prihardini, Gerardo Una and Kateryna Zhabska, "Stacking up the Benefits Lessons from India's Digital Journey" IMF Working Paper (2023).

²⁹ Rathore, Sumangla, and Avinash Panwar. "Digital-locker services in India: an assessment of user adoption and challenges." In *Leveraging Digital Innovation for Governance, Public Administration, and Citizen Services: Emerging Research and Opportunities*, pp. 101-131. IGI Global, (2020).

The RBI is responsible for regulating "payment systems" in India under the PSS Act, 2007. The PSS Act defines a "payment system" as a method that enables the transfer of payments from a payer to a beneficiary. This system encompasses services pertaining to clearing, payment, settlement, or a combination thereof. It specifically does not include stock exchanges in its definition.³⁰

- ***“The Directions for Opening and Operation of Accounts and Settlement of Payments for Electronic Payment Transactions Involving Intermediaries, 2009 (the EPT Directions) and the Guidelines on Regulation of Payment Aggregators and Payment Gateways (the PAPG Guidelines)”***: Financial intermediaries, including payment gateways and aggregators, are governed by the EPT Directions and the PAPG Guidelines. The word "intermediary" refers to businesses or individuals who act as a go-between when it comes to settling payments for products and services made online. While PGs provide the necessary technology for online payment processing, PAs make it possible for online stores and merchants to accept payments. The EPT Directions apply to many other types of companies, not limited to PAs and PGs. These include businesses that take payments via online or electronic means, service providers that enable electronic payments, and e-commerce and m-commerce platforms. Eligibility restrictions, financial needs, and technology suggestions are all included in the PAPG Guidelines. The PAPG Guidelines are a collection of suggestions on technology that are not legally obligatory on PGs. Security, data standards, risk management, fraud prevention, and technological infrastructure are all touched upon in these suggestions.³¹
- ***“The Master Direction on Issuance and Operation of Prepaid Payment Instruments (PPI Guidelines)”***³²: The ability to preload a financial instrument with a predetermined quantity of money is known as a prepaid payment instrument (PPI). After loading up, you may use it to pay for anything from groceries to bills to money transfers and more. Examples of a PPI might be a pre-paid debit or credit card, an electronic wallet, a voucher, etc. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) issued thorough PPI

³⁰ Yesha Yadav, Fintech and International Financial Regulation, 53 Vanderbilt Journal of Transnational Law. 1109 (2020)

³¹ “Fintech Laws In India: Understanding The Regulatory Regime” (Best law firm in Gurgaon - Corrida Legal, August 29, 2023) <https://www.corridalegal.com/publications/fintech-laws-in-india-understanding-the-regulatory-regime/>

³² Chhabra M, “Prepaid Instruments - An Analysis of Master Directions Issued by RBI” (Lexology, September 20, 2021) <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=0b63f19a-b9e6-4e71-8974-9d324ce820f0>

Guidelines to regulate PPIs in a way that would encourage innovation and competition while also protecting consumers and assuring their safety.

- **“The Guidelines for Licensing of Payments Banks (Payment Bank Guidelines)”**: Payment banks provide modest savings accounts and payment/remittance services to a variety of groups to foster financial inclusion. These financial institutions are public limited corporations that have their licences granted by the Banking Regulation Act of 1949. Their primary business activities are deposit-taking and money transfer services. Among the many objectives of the Payment Bank Guidelines is the establishment of minimum capital, liquidity, and governance benchmarks that payment banks are obligated to fulfil. This is to make sure that financial institutions that handle payments are adequately funded and managed responsibly.³³

B. REGULATIONS/ GUIDELINES BY THE IRDAI

Proactively promoting the implementation of fintech in the insurance industry and safeguarding the interests of policyholders and insurance product buyers, the IRDAI has responded to the growth of InsurTech. That being said, corporate agents, online aggregators, and insurance brokers are all largely governed by the IRDAI's laws in the insurance fintech sector:³⁴

- **“The Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (Registration of Corporate Agents) Regulations, 2015”**: Corporate agents mediate between prospective policyholders and insurance firms. Corporate agents engaged in the sale of life, health, and general insurance are governed by this rule, which establishes standards for their ownership, control, record keeping, registration, behaviour, and operations.
- **“The Insurance Web Aggregator Regulations, 2017”**: The purpose of this rule is to keep an eye on online aggregators that are middlemen in the insurance industry. Users can compare rates and get more information about products from different insurance providers and other pertinent issues via the websites run by these intermediaries.

³³ Legal C, “Fintech Laws In India: Understanding The Regulatory Regime” (Fin Tech - India, October 9, 2023) <https://www.mondaq.com/india/fin-tech/1369804/fintech-laws-in-india-understanding-the-regulatory-regime#:~:text=The%20objective%20of%20the%20Payment,a%20safe%20and%20sound%20manner>

³⁴ Surya, M., and Dr B. Sudha. "IRDAI-A Regulator of Insurance Business." *International Journal of Research in Advent Technology (IJRAT)*, ISSN (2019): 2321-9637.

- **“The Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (Insurance Brokers) Regulations, 2018”**: Insurance brokers mediate between policyholders and insurers to make the purchase and sale of insurance policies more seamless. By requiring insurance brokers to meet certain qualifications, such as being registered and licenced, these rules protect policyholders' interests. In addition, it specifies procedures to be followed in the event of noncompliance and governs telemarketing, distance marketing, and internet sales.

C. REGULATIONS/ GUIDELINES BY THE SEBI

In order to control the securities markets and make sure that trading is fair and honest, SEBI was given extensive powers under the **“Securities Contracts (Regulation) Act, 1956 and the Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992”**. Stockbrokers and investment advisors are subject to a number of rules put in place by SEBI to govern their activities. To guarantee that these market players maintain the required levels of expertise, professionalism, and ethics, these rules establish eligibility qualifications, mandate registration, and impose compliance-based duties.³⁵

To further promote the development of the securitization market and protect investors' interests, SEBI is involved in regulating the listing and issuance of security receipts and securitized debt instruments in India. Securities trading in the fintech industry is regulated by the **“SEBI (Alternative Investment Funds) Regulations, 2012,”** with a focus on Alternative Investment Funds (AIFs). Investment vehicles including venture capital funds, private equity funds, and other AIFs may find their footing and run according to these rules. All AIFs doing business in India must comply with the rules on investor protection, disclosure requirements, investment limits, and registration. The goal of these rules is to make sure that the fintech-driven AIF industry is open and honest with its investors.³⁶

D. OTHER SIGNIFICANT LEGISLATIONS

- **The National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI) Regulations**: The NPCI oversees a number of important Indian payment systems, including the RuPay card payment network, payment aggregators, and the UPI. The NPCI keeps an eye on

³⁵ Murali, S. Mohana. "The Role of SEBI in Protecting the Interests of Investors and Regulation of Financial Intermediaries." *International Journal for Scientific Research & Development* 5, no. 04 (2017): 1942-1954.

³⁶ Singh, Amit. "Securities and Exchange Board of India: Role of SEBI in Promoting Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) in India." *Jus Corpus LJ* 3 (2022): 468.

various payment systems to make sure they're running well and helping with transactions. The RBI Payments Vision 2025, published last year, places a strong emphasis on cross-border payments among its primary areas of concentration. A wholly-owned subsidiary of the NPCI, NPCI International Payments Limited (NIPL) is responsible for implementing RuPay and UPI services outside of India. This allows the NPCI to broaden its worldwide reach. Agreements to encourage UPI adoption have been negotiated with nations including the United Kingdom, France, Singapore, and the United Arab Emirates via bilateral collaboration.³⁷

X. NAVIGATING REGULATORY HURDLES IN INDIA'S FINTECH LANDSCAPE: PAYTM CRISES

In order to improve its services, Paytm Bank has a structure that includes strategic relationships with different universities. A maximum deposit limit of Rs. 2,000,000 is one of the limitations that consumers face, even though they may keep deposits similar to other bank accounts. It is worth mentioning that Paytm Bank has teamed up with IndusInd Bank to provide fixed deposits and with MasterCard to make it easier to issue both digital and physical debit cards. By forming strategic alliances with industry heavyweights like Tata and Aditya Birla, Paytm Bank has expanded its product offerings to include lending services. Paytm Bank stands out when it comes to loans since it approves acceptable loan requests in only 5 minutes. What makes Paytm so efficient is that it has all the paperwork needed to provide loans, including access to consumers' transaction history. The reliance of Paytm Bank's activities on other parties is shown by these partnerships.³⁸

A. Non-compliance impact:

Paytm was penalised by the RBI on January 29 for its ongoing failure to comply. A statement was issued by the RBI stating that, "aside from interest, cashbacks, or refunds that may be credited anytime," no additional deposits, credit transactions, or top-ups would be permitted in any customer accounts, prepaid instruments, wallets, FASTags, NCMC cards, etc. after

³⁷ Baj, Mitali, Yashika Rane, and Ishwari Shinde. "National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI): Overview of Innovations and Growth." *Journal of Applied Management-Jidnyasa* (2023): 23-36.

³⁸ Basu, Bibaswan, M. P. Sebastian, and Arpan Kumar Kar. "What affects the promoting intention of mobile banking services? Insights from mining consumer reviews." *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services* 77 (2024): 103695.

February 29, 2024. Here is a visual representation of all the non-compliances that Paytm Bank has committed during its history.

B. KYC Compliance Issues and Regulatory Enforcement

Customers are worried about their security and the bank's compliance with regulations after Paytm Payments Bank Ltd. (PPBL) was recently subjected to a regulatory investigation that revealed serious violations of the KYC standard.

A large number of accounts that did not comply with Know Your Customer regulations were permitted to expand by PPBL, and there were thousands of incidents where a single PAN was

used to create many accounts. Additionally, as part of the Know Your Customer process, clients were coerced into opening a Paytm bank savings account against their will.

The RBI had previously warned and instructed the bank to fix KYC flaws, but the bank's compliance was determined to be erroneous and inadequate. As a result, in March 2022, the RBI imposed supervisory limits, which included pausing the onboarding of new customers and requiring an external assessment to evaluate the system's integrity.³⁹

The seriousness of the compliance breaches is further shown by the fact that several Paytm accounts and wallets have been suspended by law authorities in response to digital fraud charges.

C. Money Laundering Concerns and Regulatory Actions

Paytm has recently been under scrutiny from regulatory bodies due to worries about possible money laundering operations and dubious transactions using its banking unit. The large number of inactive accounts has prompted the central bank to take action in response to fears that these accounts might be misused or used to facilitate illegal activity. An expert estimate that there are 35 crore e-wallets associated with Paytm Payments Bank. Roughly 31% of these would be inactive, leaving only 4% with a little or non-existent amount that may be put to use. Mule accounts may have been used by an abnormally large number of inactive accounts.

On top of everything else, there have been accusations of digital fraud, which has led law authorities to freeze many Paytm accounts and wallets. As part of their investigations into possible breaches of the “*Prevention of Money Laundering Act (PMLA)*,” the Enforcement Directorate (ED) raided PPBL and its parent firm, One97 Communications Ltd. (OCL). Suicide and other severe outcomes resulting from fraudulent digital loan transactions prompted these measures.

D. Chinese Investment and Data Security Concerns:

Data security, and more specifically the availability of sensitive user information, has come up as a result of the partnership between Paytm and Ant Group Co. Compliance with data protection legislation is crucial, especially in light of the government's monitoring of Chinese investments. However, Paytm's partnership with Ant Group Co. is still authorised, which is a

³⁹ “Towards a More Supportive Regulatory Regime” (PwC) <https://www.pwc.in/industries/financial-services/fintech/fintech-insights/towards-a-more-supportive-regulatory-regime.html>

non-compliance concern. This incident emphasises how critical it is for Paytm to strengthen its security procedures in order to reduce the likelihood of data leaks. Serious ramifications for user privacy and regulatory compliance have already resulted from ignoring these considerations.⁴⁰

E. Impact on customers:

An understanding of what is known as a nodal account is necessary before proceeding. To ease financial transactions involving several parties, an intermediate account known as a nodal account might be used. When it comes to money, a nodal account is like a central vault; it holds all the cash until they're ready to be distributed. Financial institutions, online retailers, and payment processors all make use of this setup to control and direct the movement of money. Transparency and accountability in financial dealings are provided by nodal accounts, which are vital for the effective and seamless execution of transactions.⁴¹

So, whereas banks serve as the nodal account for other UPI payment applications, Paytm's banks serve as the nodal service providers.

Particularly affecting customers' capacity to do business via Paytm, the new regulatory moves have far-reaching consequences. Customers will still be able to send and receive payments inside the app until February 29. Nevertheless, beyond this date, consumers will only be allowed to access their Paytm wallet or Paytm Payments Bank account to make withdrawals or transfers of cash until their available amount is exhausted. Services including AEPS, IMPS, and UPI money transfers will no longer be available, and new deposits or top-ups to the bank account or wallet will not be permitted, per regulatory regulations. Importantly, all accounts are restricted from making transactions since they are all tied to Paytm Payments Bank as their nodal account. You will still be able to use, withdraw, or transfer the money on prepaid instruments like Fastag and NCMC cards that the bank has issued, but starting on March 1, you will not be able to add any more funds to these accounts. When thinking about retailers, the impact of this is enormous. For instance, all of the offered sound boxes and QR codes have been connected to the payments bank, and the process of altering all of them is rather unpredictable; there are around 37 million of them.⁴²

⁴⁰ He, Yujia. "Chinese Fintech Goes Global: Political Challenges and Business Strategies." *Asia Policy* 19, no. 1 (2024): 35-50.

⁴¹ "The Paytm Crisis: Regulatory Actions, Compliance Issues, and Consumer Impact," (Penaite, February 15), 2024 <https://penaite.com/the-paytm-crisis-regulatory-actions-compliance-issues-and-consumer-impact/>

⁴² <https://inc42.com/buzz/live-updates-everything-about-paytms-crisis/>

This is how Paytm's consumers are impacted.

XI. CONCLUSION

Digital payments in India have seen exponential growth, driven by government policies like Digital India and India Stack, rising internet and smartphone penetration, and innovation by fintech players. However, the legislative and regulatory framework governing digital payments has struggled to keep pace with the rapid changes.

The research indicates several gaps and limitations in the current framework, centred around the Payment and Settlement Systems Act 2007. With the evolution of the payments landscape, especially the emergence of new payment instruments and providers, the Act has proved inadequate in providing guidance on issues like consumer protection, promoting competition and innovation, security and interoperability standards.

Specific regulations around critical areas like data privacy, information security, and grievance redressal mechanisms also remain ambiguous or fragmented across sectoral guidelines. The recent Data Protection Bill 2021 also leaves gaps around applicability to non-personal or financial data. This has led RBI to issue multiple circulars and directions to fill regulatory vacuums, resulting in overlaps.

India must enact a new, consolidated Payments Act aligned with the dynamic digital ecosystem. Such legislation should adopt a principle and risk-based approach, defining payment systems and services distinctly. It needs to balance prudential oversight on system stability risks with open access and innovation in competitive payment offerings.

Robust data governance frameworks encompassing privacy, ownership, portability and security are pivotal alongside cyber resilience strategies to build user trust. The RBI and sector participants should enhance the adoption of global data standards, and enable seamless data flows between payment systems while preventing misuse and fostering data transparency.

Finally, long-term policy vision coupled with public-private collaboration is key to unlocking sustainable payment system growth. With smartphone and internet penetration set to increase in the coming years, especially in rural areas, innovative payment solutions can effectively promote financial inclusion. However, this necessitates proportional, calibrated regulations allowing responsibly supervised innovation in customer-centric payment services.